

CARACTERÍSTICAS MORFOLÓGICAS E ANATÔMICAS DOS ESTADOS ETÁRIOS DE *Scutellaria stevenii* Juz. (*Scutellaria orientalis* subsp. *orientalis*) EM FITOCENOSES DA CRIMEIA DE ENCOSTAS**MORPHOLOGICAL AND ANATOMICAL FEATURES OF AGE STATES OF *Scutellaria stevenii* Juz. (*Scutellaria orientalis* subsp. *orientalis*) IN PHYTOCOENOSES OF THE CRIMEA FOOTHILLS****МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И АНАТОМИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВОЗРАСТНЫХ СОСТОЯНИЙ *Scutellaria stevenii* Juz. (*Scutellaria orientalis* subsp. *Orientalis*) В ФИТОЦЕНОЗАХ ПРЕДГОРИЙ КРЫМА**

VAKHRUSHEVA, Lyudmila P.^{1*}; ABDULGANIEVA, Elvira F.²; AKHKIYAMOVA, Guzeliya R.³, SHICHIYAKH, Rustem A.⁴; AVDEEV, Yuri M.⁵

^{1,2}V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University, Faculty of Biology and Chemistry. Russian Federation.

³Naberezhnye Chelny State Pedagogical University, Naberezhnye Chelny, Russian Federation.

⁴Kuban State Agrarian University named after I.T. Trubilin, Russian Federation.

⁵Vologda State University, Vologda. Russian Federation.

* Corresponding author
e-mail:vakhl@inbox.ru

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RESUMO

Os recursos de implementação do ciclo de vida para a maioria das plantas são específicos da espécie, o que se reflete em uma mudança nas esferas morfológicas, anatômicas e fisiológicas da planta. Um estudo da ontogenese das plantas permite uma compreensão mais profunda das características coenóticas da população e do grau de influência do meio ambiente na implementação da ontomorfogênese das plantas. Este trabalho é dedicado ao estudo do ciclo de vida de uma das espécies taxonomicamente controversas de Crimeia - *Scutellaria stevenii* Juz. O estudo da ontogênese de *Scutellaria stevenii* foi realizado na natureza e para mudas e indivíduos jovens em laboratório. Os princípios de identificação e contabilização de critérios qualitativo-quantitativos foram utilizados para identificar características morfológicas características de vários estados etários. O estudo da estrutura anatômica dos órgãos vegetativos (raiz, caule, brotação) foi realizado com preparações temporárias de um tecido vivo, com métodos padrão. Nesse estudo, o ciclo de vida de *Scutellaria stevenii* contém 4 períodos ontogenéticos e 10 estados etários, que são realizados na ontogenese total ou parcial. No caso de desenvolvimento normal, a ontogênese dos genetes dura de 10 a 16 anos. Em indivíduos virgens que crescem em ecótopos móveis, foi encontrado um tipo de desenvolvimento polivariável. Indivíduos polvariantes formam o arbusto primário com xilorzomas de diferentes comprimentos que exercem a função de fixação adicional no solo e a formação de arbustos parciais que perdem sua conexão com o indivíduo primário pela idade geradora. A capacidade de indivíduos pré-regenerativos de se estabelecer vegetativamente pode ser considerada como adaptação compensatória devido à alta morte de mudas em fitocenoses naturais. As características anatômicas do caule e da raiz de várias idades indicam a partição incompleta morfológica não expressa. Esses critérios são uma adição importante à identificação morfológica da idade.

Palavras-chave: ciclo de vida, tipo de desenvolvimento polivariável, Crimeia.

ABSTRACT

The life cycle implementation features for most plants are species-specific, which is reflected in a change in the morphological, anatomical and physiological spheres of the plant. A study of plant ontogenesis allows a deeper understanding of both the coenotic features of the population and the degree of influence of the environment on the implementation of plant ontomorphogenesis. This work is devoted to the study of the life cycle of one of the taxonomically controversial species for Crimea - *Scutellaria stevenii* Juz. Ontogenesis study of

Scutellaria stevenii was carried out in nature and for seedlings and juvenile individuals in a laboratory. The concept of a discrete description of ontogenesis was used to describe the life cycle of *Scutellaria stevenii*, under which to revealed a group of anatomical and morphological features characteristic of each ontogenetic state. The study of the anatomical structure of the vegetative organs (root, stem, flower-bearing shoot) was carried out using temporary preparations of a living tissue with standard methods. In this study the life cycle of *Scutellaria stevenii* contains 4 ontogenetic periods and 10 age states, which are realized in full or partial ontogenesis. In the case of normal development, ontogenesis of genets lasts 10-16 years. In virginal individuals growing on mobile ecotopes, a polyvariant type of development have been found. Polyvariant individuals form the primary bush with xylorizomes of different lengths which carry the function of additional fixation in the soil and the formation of partial bushes that lose their connection with the primary individual by the generative age. The ability of pregenerative individuals to vegetatively established in our study can be considered as compensatory adaptation due to the high death of seedlings in natural phytocoenoses. The anatomical features of the stem and root of various age states to identify morphologically unexpressed incomplete partition. These criteria is an important addition to the morphological identification of age.

Keywords: *life cycle, polyvariant type of development, Crimea.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Особенности реализации жизненного цикла для большинства растений видоспецифичны, что отражается в изменении морфологической, анатомической и физиологической сферах растения. Изучение онтогенеза растений проводится с целью более глубокого понимания, как ценотических черт популяции, так и для выяснения степени влияния среды обитания на реализацию онтоморфогенеза растения. Данное исследование посвящено изучению жизненного цикла одного из таксономически спорных для Крыма видов – *Scutellaria stevenii* Juz. Изучение онтогенеза *Scutellaria stevenii* проводилось в природе и частично (проростков и ювенильных особей) в лаборатории. Для описания жизненного цикла шлемника Стевена использована концепция дискретного описания онтогенеза, согласно которой выявляется группа анатомо-морфологических признаков, характерных для каждого онтогенетического состояния. Исследование анатомической структуры проводилось с помощью временных препаратов, изготовленных вручную с использованием живых растений стандартными методами. В жизненном цикле *Scutellaria stevenii* выделено 4 онтогенетических периода и 10 возрастных состояний, которые реализуются в форме полного или частичного онтогенеза; в случае нормального развития онтогенез генеты длится 10-16 лет. У виргинильных особей, произрастающих на подвижных экотопах, обнаружен поливариантный тип развития, при котором первичный куст образует различной длины ксилоризомы, несущие функцию дополнительного закрепления в почве и образования парциальных кустов, которые к генеративному возрасту теряют связь с материнской особью. Установленная в нашем исследовании способность особей прегенеративного периода к вегетативному размножению, может рассматриваться как компенсаторная адаптация, обусловленная высокой гибелью проростков в естественных фитоценозах. В анатомическом строении корня и побега наблюдается неполная, морфологически невыраженная партикуляция, ограниченная, главным образом, зоной корневой шейки и базальной части главного корня. Эти критерии являются важным дополнением к морфологической идентификации возраста.

Ключевые слова: *жизненный цикл, поливариантность развития, Крым.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Scutellaria L. - the numerous polymorphic genus of the family Lamiaceae (Labiatae) has more than 460 species according to the APG II system (The Plant List, 2019). *Scutellaria* genus presented to 5 species *S. albida* L. subsp. *albida*, *S. albida* subsp. *colchica* (Rech. f.) J.R. Edm., *S. altissima* L., *S. galericulata* L. and *S. orientalis* L. subsp. *orientalis* in the Crimea (2,3). Species composition of the genus *Scutellaria* has always had controversial issues, some of which continue to the present, especially regarding the intraspecific structure of *S. orientalis* L. (Pichugin, 2011; Yena, 2012).

Five Crimea endemic species *S. heterochroa* Juz., *S. hypopolia* Juz., *S. hirtella* Juz., *S. taurica* Juz. and *S. stevenii* Juz. were described by S. Yuzepchuk independent of *S. orientalis* based on morphological differences in the structure of the leaf blade and the pubescent character (Komarov, 1954). Such an opinion was supported and reflected in the summary of the flora of the Crimea peninsula by E. V. Wulf (1966) and V. Golubev (1996). The opposite view was expressed by D. Dobrochaeva, M. Kotov (Mosyakin, Fedoronchuk, 1999), according to which, described by S. Yuzepchuk, species

should be considered a different geographical race of *S. orientalis* (Yena, 2012). A similar trend is also incorporated in the last review of the flora of Crimea, in which the species is listed as *S. orientalis* L. subsp. *orientalis*. However, recent studies have shown a more complicated composition of *S. orientalis* distributed in the peninsula and the possibility of isolating distinct species. Such disagreements indicate the need for detailed research of the genus *Scutellaria* in the Crimea and the search for diagnostic value more "strong" keys for the differentiation of species (Pichugin, 2012).

Biomorphological features act as additional taxonomic criteria for distinguishing species (Savinykh et al.; Notov and Kusnetzova, 2004). At present, the life cycles of *Scutellaria* species growing on the territory of the Russian Federation have been described for *S. baicalensis* Georgi (Banaeva, 2000), *S. tuvensis* Juz., *S. galericulata* L., *S. supina* L., *S. tuvensis* Juz. (Guseva, 2013a,b,c,d).

The goal of this study was to identify the anatomical and morphological features of the age states of the life cycle of a well-differentiated species *S. stevenii*. The data on this ornamental plant is scarce and mainly concerns its distribution on the peninsula (Pichugin, 2012). The keys proposed by V. Pichugin for identifying 6 disputed subtaxa, among which *S. stevenii* is also included are not sufficiently convincing and need further clarification.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The classification of life forms of higher plants by I. G. Serebryakova (1954; 1964) and Savinykh (2015) was adopted as the basis for the identification of types of biomorphs. The definition of the type of ontogenesis and variants of polyvariant development was carried out according to the classifications proposed by L. A. Zhukova (1983; 1995; 2001; 2013). At the heart of the allocation of age groups was the idea of T.A. Rabotnov (1950) about the division of the life cycle into four periods: latent (dormant seed time); virginal (from seed germination to reproduction of an individual in a generative way); generative; senile (senile). Rabotnov's ideas were supplemented by Uranov (1975) and his followers (Coenopopulations of plants ..., 1976, 1988; Nukhimovsky 1997; Ontogenetic Atlas ..., 1997, 2000, 2002, 2004; Zlobin (2012) as a result the modern periodization of the life cycle includes 4 periods, 2 subperiods

(embryonic and latent) and 12 ontogenetic ages: seeds (se), juvenile (j), immature (im), virgin (v), early (g_1), mature (g_2), later (g_3) generative states, subsenile (ss) and senile (s) states).

The life cycle of *S. stevenii* was monitored at the 3 years in two natural populations growing in the foothill Crimea. The sample of plants for each age group was 30 individuals. Morphological parameters were measured in the natural population (Cheremisina et al., 2017, 2018). Seedlings and partially juvenile plants were observed in conditions of artificial cultivation.

Before germination, the seeds were sterilized in 3% hydrogen peroxide solution for 10 min and 70% ethanol for 1 min and then washed in 3 times 45 minutes in sterile distilled water. Then the seeds were transferred to a moistened filter paper, 50 pieces each, in sterile Petri dishes, and placed in a thermostat at 20-30. Seed germination was conducted in 2-fold repetition. Seed germination was determined on the seventh day (GOST, 2011; Zaripova, 2016)

Conclusions about the age of plants were taken based on the degree of xylem development and the number of annual rings of the primary root and stem. Anatomical cuts were carried out on live drugs (preparations) with 3-5 multiples for each age condition. Floroglucin dye was used to stain xylem tissues (Lotova, 2001; Barikina, 2004; Serebryakova, 2006). The microscopy of permanent and temporary preparations was carried out using the Olympus CX31RTSF microscope. The objects were photofixed by the Olympus digital camera (Industrial Digital Camera TOUPCAMTM U3CMOS10000KPA).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Scutellaria stevenii is a erosulate dwarf-shrub growing in tomillars and petrophytic steppes of the foothills, where it can perform the function of a dominant, and often determining the structure of phytocoenoses (Abdulganieva, 2013). In the spatial and ecological distribution, this species is mainly found to sloping calcareous gravelly and marl ecotopes. *S. stevenii* is morphologically close to the species *S. taurica* and different from it short tomentose pubescence of the stem and petioles. The upper side of leaves is rarely tomentose gray-green and densely white-tomentose with completely hidden veins in the underside. Leaf margins have

shorter and broader straight teeth (Komarov, 1954).

3.1. Latent and Pre-generative periods

In connection with the arisen difficulties of finding the seedlings in the natural environment, observation of this age was carried out in artificial conditions. **Seeds (se)** are small (2x1 mm), oval in shape, compressed laterally. Seed peel densely pubescent with short hairs due to the seeds are gray. Seed germination was determined on the seventh day, and it averaged 10%, which explains the difficulty of finding the seedlings in the natural phytocenosis. This low percent of germination can be attributed to the lack of endosperm in the seeds of the Lamiaceae family. The **seedlings (p)** have rounded cotyledons (at the time of opening 0.4 x 0.4 cm), are painted green. The development of the 2nd pair of leaves occurs at 4-5 days after planting in the soil. They, in contrast to the cotyledons, have a peristolped form with 3 lobes on each side (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Seedlings of *S. stevenii*.

In seedlings formed 1-5 leaves of similar shape. The emergence of seedlings in nature is timed to the end of February - March of the spring period or the end of September - October of the autumn period of germination.

In the case of normal development, by the end of the first month, the seedlings acquire the features of a **juvenile age (j)**. Their distinctive feature is the absence of cotyledons and the active appearance of leaves with 3 toothed lobes, which then die off successively, and well-marked scars remain in their place. The duration of this age from 2.5 to 3 months (Figure 2).

Figure 2. *S. stevenii* juvenile individuals.

Plants of **immature age (im)** are distinguished by the appearance of leaves with 4 toothed lobes on each side of the leaf blade (Figure 3). The position of the epicotyl and hypocotyl is typically perpendicular to the soil surface, but they can greatly change the angle of inclination due to the peculiarities of the microrelief of the territory. At immature age the individuals of *S. stevenii* leave for the 1st wintering period.

Figure 3. *S. stevenii* immature individual.

At 2-3 years of the life cycle of the plant enters a **virginal age (v)**, (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Virgin *S. stevenii*.

In this age, all the vegetative features of the adult plant are already formed: the leaves are ovate, along the edge are deeply crenate-toothed, with wide, straight, 5-7 teeth on each side. Lateral growth branches develop at this age - usually after winter (less often summer) dormancy. The first leaves of lateral branches are morphologically similar to the leaves of a seedling or juvenile plant.

There are signs of polyvariant development of life cycle. Individuals growing on a horizontal surface of the relief go through 2 stages of morphogenesis: 1) primary shoot ($p \rightarrow j \rightarrow im$); 2) the primary bush ($v \rightarrow g_1 \rightarrow g_2 \rightarrow g_3 \rightarrow ss \rightarrow s$). With the growth of individuals on movable soils of the slopes, virginal plants form different lengths (from 5-30 cm) xylorrhizoma, on which developing secondary bushes. In this type of life cycle, an individual has 3 stages of development: 1) primary shoot ($p \rightarrow j \rightarrow im$); 2) primary bush (v), 3) secondary bush ($g_1 \rightarrow g_2 \rightarrow g_3 \rightarrow ss \rightarrow s$), resulting from the destruction of xylorrhizoma between primary and secondary bushes (Figure 5).

Figure 5. *S. stevenii* life cycle scheme
1 – primary shoot; 2 – primary bush; 3 – partial bush.

The formation of this kind of rhizomes and secondary bushes provides a more vigorous fixation plant in the soil, the conquest of free

space. It compensates for the almost complete absence of sexual reproduction associated with the mass death of seedlings in a natural ecotope.

The general scheme of development of the pregenerative stage is shown in Figure 6, 7.

Figure 6. The scheme of the pregenerative period *S. stevenii*. a – seedling; b – juvenile plant; c – immature; d, e – virginal.

Figure 7. Variants of development of *S. stevenii* virginal individuals. a - formation of partial bushes on xylorrhizoma; b - virginal individual, preserving the structure of the primary bush.

3.2. Generative period

Young generative plants (g_1) are characterized by such an important feature as the loss of the connection of the parent plant with young bushes (particulas) that were formed in the virginal period of the life cycle. G_1 usually has 2-3 woody branches of renewal, which can form 1-2 generative shoots (second-order growth axis). After flowering, the grassy part of generative shoots dies, and their woody bases begin to branch, giving the 3rd order growth axes.

S. stevenii generative shoots are monocyclic, and by the next spring, they die entirely until the lateral shoot but remain in contact with the parent plant. Therefore, in g_1 individuals, shoots of the 2nd and 3rd orders remain capable of flowering, but the flowering shoots number is small (1-3). The flowers number in the inflorescence is 4-7. The main root is thickened, and the first signs of partitioning are noted in the anatomical structure. A large number of adventitious roots are formed. The root systems of young bushes are intensively developed, creating the secondary root system. The generative shoots formation and their transition to flowering in young bushes occur 1-2 years later than the primary individual. The duration of this age phase is 2-3 years (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Young generative individual.

Mature generative (middle-aged) individuals (g_2) are represented by a compact dwarf-shrub, composed of 18–20 mixed-age renewal growth axes, of which 1/3 (sometimes 1/2) are represented by generative shoots with 9–11 flowers. The lower parts of the perennial shoots begin to form the plagiotropic part, but at the same time, the compactness of the general structure of the dwarf-shrub is preserved. The function of the plagiotropic part is provided by dwarf-shrub regeneration and construction of the new above-ground growth axes. The fourth growth axes begin to appear. Some of the second-order shoots, in the basal part, acquires an oblique orthotropic position. On this part, a large number of renewal buds appear, from which can develop generative shoots or new renewal axes. The observed anatomical structure of the root shows the beginning of the particion process in the mature generative plant. In this age, phase plant remains 2-4 years (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Mature generative (middle-aged) individual.

Older generative plants (g_3) are generally losing dwarf-shrub. At the base of vegetative and generative shoots, there is a distinctly pronounced plagiotropic part; therefore, spatially shoots acquire an ascending structure. The number of generative shoots decreases (less than 1/4 of the total), and the number of dead shoots of previous years increases, especially in the central part of the caudex. Also, the number of flowers in the inflorescence is reduced to 5-7. The degree of branching decreases only occasionally shoots of the 4th order of branching occur. The growth of shoots occurs mostly on the periphery of the dwarf-shrub. The bush becomes less dense, the main root twists along the central axis. In the root, anatomical partition processes continue. In this age phase, the plant remains 2-4 years (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Older generative plants individual.

In **sub-senile plants (ss)**, primary growth axes are intensively dying. Plant height is 15–20 cm. In this phase, dwarf-shrub is preserved by 4–6 principal axes along the periphery of the bush, branching only in the upper part (3–4 shoots). There are 1-3 generative shoots; buds contain no more than 2-3 flowers. The adventitious roots do not develop, which reduces the ability of reproduction of the new lateral roots. The particioning process in the anatomical structure of the primary root is more progressive. The

duration of this age phase is 1-2 years (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Sub-senile individual.

In individuals of the **senile age (s)**, generative shoots are not formed. In this phase, processes of the elimination of primary aerial axes and lateral roots increase. A perennial woody base, up to 3-5 cm in diameter, is formed from the basal parts of dead shoots. The height of the aboveground portion is 8-12 cm. The size of the leaf blade is significantly reduced, but the number of teeth (5-7 tooth), which is typical for adult generative plants, remains the same (Figure 12). The duration of this age phase is 1 year.

Figure 12. Senile individual.

3.3. The anatomical structure of the stem and root.

The lower ligneous part of the generative shoot is covered with secondary dermal tissue - periderm. Phellem (cork cells) has longitudinal gaps and consists of 3-4 layers of dead cells. Under periderm, there are 5-6 layers of parenchymal cells of the cortex. Phloem with poorly developed mechanical tissue surrounds the xylem in a continuous layer. The conducting elements of xylem are represented by radial rows of vessels separated by thin medullary rays and xylem fibers. In the center - the pith with a well-

defined perimedullary zone, including elements of the primary xylem (Figure 13).

Figure 13. A – cross-section of the generative shoot of *S. stevenii*. *sx* – secondary xylem; *cm* – cambium; *c* – core, *px* – primary xylem; *ppc* – parenchyma of the primary cortex; *pzc* – perimedullary zone of the core; *pr* – periderm; *fl* – phloem, (15x20).

The main root is covered with a multilayer periderm of subepidermal origin, (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Cross-section of the main root of the generative individual *S. stevenii*. *sx*-secondary xylem; *sfl* – secondary phloem; *cm* – cambium; *pc* – primary cortex; *px* – primary xylem; *pr* – parenchymal ray; *p* – periderm (15x20).

The outer layers of the cork are formed of 3-6 rows of cells. Under the periderm, there are remnants of the cortex, formed by thin-walled cells elongated in the tangential direction (5-7 rows). After the inner layer of the cortex is functioning phloem. Narrow single-row rays

separate the xylem vessels in the radial direction. Between the conducting elements are located with non-woody fibers of the libriform

In the anatomical structure of the root of generative plants, signs of partition were found, the initial stages of which can be observed at 5-7 years of age in young generative individuals. In this age, the central cylinder in the cross-section becomes asymmetric, acquiring lobed outlines (Figure 15, A). The processes of xylem separation continue intensively along with the radial rays, and in the old generative individuals, they reach the middle of the stele. (Figure 15, B). The distance between the xylem segments is filled with parenchymal tissue. In some cases, the xylem is completely separating, forming small islands surrounded by parenchymal tissue (Figure 15, D). The processes of destruction of living tissues begin in the center of the cylinder and continue in the centrifugal direction, capturing the wood parenchyma and the parenchyma of radial rays. Dead tissue areas are don't coloring (Figure 15, C, E).

Figure 15. Anatomical features of root (A-E) and shoot (F) *S. stevenii* partition, (15x40).

Particle starts as a result of the spreading of traces of dead shoots to the root collar and further to the taproot. Partition of the shoot is visible in Figure 15 (F). The abundance of mechanical elements in the wood of the root and the long-term functioning of the growth axes determine the incomplete, morphologically unexpressed particularization, mainly limited by the root neck area and the basal part of the main root.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

The leaf morphology and the teeth number of *S. stevenii* leaf blade are the main features of differentiation the preregenerative

period into 5 age states; the three age states (g_1 , g_2 and g_3) of generative period are differentiated by habitus, branch axes of 2-4th orders, the ratio of generative and vegetative shoots, and the number of flowers. In the senile period included two age-related states (s, ss) are differentiate according to the intensity of branching, partition and dying of the aboveground skeletal axes; the early stages of shrubs partition are clearly correspond to the anatomical features. The vegetative reproduction in the preregenerative period is a compensatory adaptation respond to the high flexibility of seedlings in natural phytocoenoses. This indicates a high ecological and morphological plasticity of the species due to a change in realization of ontogenesis. The primary taxonomic criteria for intraspecific differences between *S. stevenii* and *S. orientalis* are the presence of xylorizome, vegetative reproduction at virgin age and differences in the teeth number of leaf margin.

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